

Corporate Social Responsibility in Palestinian Public Schools

Author's Details:

Muayad Alhih¹, Abdul Malek Bin A. Tambi², Ali Ibrahim Abueid³
(1)(2)(3) Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin

* Correspondence: malekahmad@yahoo.com

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Abstract

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) programs for the development of schools and the improvement of students' skills in Palestine are limited. This study aims to develop a holistic concept of CSR that accommodates the educational streams in Palestinian schools, namely: sciences, social sciences, as well as commercial and vocational training. The study identifies the obstacles experienced by companies in implementing CSR activities, such as the complexity of administrative procedures imposed by the Ministry of Education. The authors suggest the means by which CSR activities could be improved, developed, and implemented for the sustainability of excellence in school education. Descriptive approach is used to determine the extent of the implementation of CSR in the schools. A qualitative approach is used to describe the weaknesses and strengths of the institutions and companies participating in CSR projects in government schools. Data are sourced from school reports on projects undertaken by the participating institutions and companies. Other sources of data include Arabic and foreign articles and periodicals. The study highlights various perspectives of CSR in schools. The study found that the CSR projects are related to infrastructure development or support of certain educational programs. There is no difference in community participation and philanthropy involvements in CSR activities. There are a number of obstacles faced by institutions and companies, including financial and technical limitations, administrative procedures at schools, and federal government laws and regulations. Also, the mechanism of applying corporate social responsibility varies according to the objectives and potential of each institution and company and the prevailing environment. The institutions and companies have a specific duty to serve society by way of facilitating the sustainability, development, and growth of school education through CSR. Charitable work and community participation are open, and any company can participate

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Schools, Education, training

1. Introduction

In education, the dimension of CSR can be used for the benefit of both companies and society. This could improve the reputation of the companies, increase the loyalty of their employees, and increase the local talent (Robertson, 2017). The Palestinian schools are one of the most important pillars of the educational system. The importance of education has called on leaders, educators, and practitioners of education all over the world to reconsider its form and content and try to renew its objectives and systems, content, methods, paths, and methods of assessment. Therefore, many conferences and seminars have been held at the international, regional and local levels to discuss one or more of the issues surrounding the modernization and development of the educational system (Diab, 2010).

In Palestine, secondary education witnessed a series of innovations and changes in its structure, programs, and assessment system. However, the Palestinian Ministry of Education and Higher Education is striving to prepare the Palestinian students to engage in real life. The ministry's vision for the coming three years (2019-2022) is to concentrate on vocational education. Therefore, the schools are in great need to involve their students in institutions and companies for training programs (Makhlouf, 2012).

In Palestine, education faces many challenges that prevent the achievement of educational goals. These challenges include a lack of skilled employees for the required jobs and absence of training programs capable of providing basic skills to students, as well as the centrality of educational decision-making. The process of societal development stems from the performance of schools, which is considered the basic pillar of sustainable development. Accordingly, the importance of CSR lies in enhancing education and removing obstacles to the progress of the educational process (Al-Qurashi, 2011).

The school community as one of the stakeholders in CSR programs seems to have been ignored as a basic component in the process (Ismail et al., 2013), especially in Palestine. Due to its broad meaning, the CSR could mean a program, an initiative, or any working together between a company and a school through which dual benefits are gained by both sides.

In this study, the projects of institutions and companies were studied in the schools under the Directorate of Education and Higher Education in northern Hebron: (104) schools implemented (263) projects in the region, institutions (80), companies (7), local community (112), schools (12), Directorate of Education (29), and the Ministries (23) projects. According to the type of project, educational projects amount to 143 while infrastructure projects constitute 120. These are used as a model to develop a holistic concept of CSR in Palestinian institutions and companies that accommodate the educational streams in Palestinian schools. The study determines the effectiveness of the partnership between Palestinian schools and companies in the implementation of CSR. It identifies the obstacles experienced by companies in implementing CSR activities.

Research Background and Research Questions

Globally, most of CSR studies in education have been conducted in higher education institutions (Naeem & Peach, 2011). There are several studies conducted in schools across different regions in the world. For example, Ismail et al. (2013) studied the types of CSR program and its influence on school development in Malaysia from the perspective of teachers. In addition, Kikkoman investigates the CSR practices of communication with public schools related to a new food education law in Japan (Takano, 2017). Similarly, Mathar (2010) explored the practices of integrating the earth convention into educational activities in Germany.

The available research on CSR programs in Palestine is limited. Some few studies conducted in this area include Alsenawi and Banat's (2014) study on CSR program in Palestine Exchange and its practices in Palestine and Jordan. Barakat et al. (2014) determined the formal institutional factors that can influence CSR disclosure. Also, a study conducted by Zaghaf (2011) focused on the concept of CSR and reviewed the forms of social responsibility and methods of CSR in Palestinian companies. The study discussed the experiences of some entrepreneurs in the field of CSR. Another study was carried out by Abu Samra (2009) to identify the obstacles to the disclosure of social responsibility. In addition, Makhoul (2012) determined the importance of social responsibility in Palestinian university education.

Despite the aforementioned research on CSR programs, more research on CSR programs is needed to resolve the complex relationships between businesses and society, including schools (Lee 2008). This study discusses the development of schools in Palestine, which is one of the tools that lead to the advancement of society and upgrading it. The study focuses on CSR in all its activities in Palestinian schools, which can be achieved by responding to the following research questions.

1. What is the concept of corporate social responsibility in the Palestinian institutions and companies?
2. How effective is the partnership between Palestinian schools and companies in the implementation of social responsibility?
3. What are the obstacles facing Palestinian schools and companies in implementing their CSR activities?
4. What are the most important suggestions for improving, developing, and implementing CSR activities in Palestinian schools?

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

The significance of CSR can never be overemphasized. It has been a subject of discussion in theory development and research. CSR has developed globally amongst academicians and practitioners (Carroll & Shabana, 2010) and in both developed and developing countries (Jamali & Karam, 2016). There are several dimensions of CSR, including the economic dimension, in which profit is an essential aspect. Another dimension is the social dimension that focuses on the well-being of the society in which the companies

operate. Also, there is an environmental dimension which takes into consideration the environmental effects of CSR operations and products (Hamouri, 2009).

The theoretical perspective of CSR can be broadly classified into political theories, social theories, and economic theories. The economic theories include positive accounting theory, agency theory, and decision-usefulness theory, which incorporate the economic aspects of CSR practice defining the market outcomes of CSR disclosure (Fernando & Lawrence, 2014). CSR is used by managers as a tool of strategies for responding to regulations, maintaining the standards, building the company's reputation and customer loyalty, which could increase profitability and help in achieving the company's objectives (Hamidu et al., 2015).

The CSR stems from the economic direction and its benefit, as well as the satisfaction of all stakeholders to improve the companies and to achieve a good relation with the society. Therefore, the responsibility of the institutions and companies for the effect of their activities on society forced them to implement CSR. Morally, they have to respect the laws, regulations, and treaties concluded with the various parties to do their function well. Therefore, they are supposed to go into a real partnership with the society to incorporate their concerns into society, environmental, and ethical issues by respecting human rights and consumers in both their operational activities and development of strategies (Commission Européenne, 2011).

CSR can be defined as moral conduct of an enterprise or a company at the direction of the society. It includes the conduct of the responsible administration in its dealings with interested parties who have a legitimate interest in the business and not just the shareholders (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2004, p. 27). Also, Smith (2011) defined CSR as "a business system that enables the production and distribution of wealth for the betterment of its stakeholders through the implementation and integration of ethical systems and sustainable management practices."

The companies believe in CSR practices and its influence on their business performance. The practices of CSR are not new as they date back to the 17th and 18th centuries, where their business philosophy was not profit maximization. During that time, CSR was practiced only to add value to society. The business is a part of the society, and they are not separated from each other (Moon, 2002). The CSR practices include internal practices that involved the employees and human capital, management of change, as well as health and safety. On the other hand, the external CSR practices for companies include business partners and suppliers, public authorities, customers, local communities, and the environment (Vázquez et al., 2013).

Drawing on this theorized societal obligation, the CSR strategies of companies depend on their financial performance. The companies may be capable of implementing CSR strategies to attract consumers and thereby increasing the value of the company. Therefore, the companies need to determine how to attract certain groups by making sense of their attitudes to social responsibility to translate that into actions (Jones et al., 2017).

Corporate Social Responsibility and Education

There are several reasons for the importance of working to strengthen the role of social responsibility in public school education to achieve national and educational objectives. The most important of these reasons is that education in Palestine has undergone difficult and complicated circumstances. In this regard, the occupation of Palestine has always tried to widen the gap between education and the local community by preventing human capacities from developing themselves and preventing them from becoming a productive part of the society. Rather, they encourage skilled individuals to emigrate (Sufian, 2010).

The educational institutions, since their inception, have been subjected to various difficulties because of the unstable and volatile life. There is disruption of classroom activities and inactivation of CSR orderly and clearly. Besides, there is a lack of developed bodies that organize social responsibility in Palestine and lack of attention to CSR at the internal and external levels in different ways (Diab, 2010).

In spite of the widespread concept of CSR and the growing interest and desire to achieve it, the level of Palestine's interest in CSR is still low, confusing and unclear. This could be due to the lack of familiarity of

Palestinian companies with the benefits and the principles of CSR. In addition, there is a lack of a clearly structured and comprehensive strategic plan that sets priorities for CSR (Saleh, 2009).

CSR in education supports educational institutions and is based primarily on achieving intellectual and ethical advancement of societies through various convictions and through the provision of mechanisms. This could enhance the chances of success and express the responsibility of companies and institutions for the impact of their decisions and activities on society and environment through transparent, ethical conduct (Diab, 2010).

Companies have an opportunity to construct regional collaboration with governments, educational institutions, and non-profits (Camilleri, 2016). This relationship could lead to the development of infrastructure, performance, and output of the educational institutions, especially the schools, by providing facilities for qualitative education. CSR in education plays an important role in decreasing the skills gap with the large experimentation. In this process, individuals, companies, and society can benefit from CSR practices (Sabeena & Krishnamoorthi, 2016).

Towards an Integrative Relationship between Education and Society

The relationship between educational institutions and society is an integral issue of interest all over the world. Besides, educational institutions must be consistent with development plans. Also, the relationship between educational institutions and society remains unclear. Educational institutions are still unable to build interactive relationships with the institutions of society, but still living an isolated community life (Hassan, 2007).

The relationship between educational institutions and society is not the graduation and teaching of students only, but also the function of educational institutions to strengthen the students' connection with society. This relationship transforms the trained human resources and produces research for the benefit of society. The relationship between educational institutions and society is a precondition for development. This is because a society without being closely linked to educational institutions cannot be developed (Diab, 2010).

CSR plays a key role in developing the local environment and touches people's lives by developing talents, helping young people to reach sustainable solutions to improve their skills, and taking care of students' health, environmental awareness, and staff development.

Obstacles to Corporate Social Responsibility

There are several obstacles to corporate social responsibility, including internal obstacles that can be controlled, such as the prevailing culture and how to deal with it, the social and environmental costs, and the management of the company to understand the CSR and carry out its duty towards the stakeholders (Kontaxi, 2004).

The external factors are the result of the environment and the conditions under which the company operates. These factors include legislation, laws, and regulations within the society. They also consist of the role that the government may play in encouraging the accounting and disclosure of information of social significance, community pressure organizations, and the extent of the company's commitment to CSR and environmental issues (Jamali, 2007).

2. Results

2.1 Analysis of the Research Questions

This study aimed to identify the social responsibility of companies and institutions in schools by answering the research questions.

1. What is the concept of corporate social responsibility for the Palestinian companies and institutions?

The analysis in this study revealed that there is a confusion about the relationship between the concept of CSR, community participation, and charity work. Most of the schools, institutions, and companies that have been visited have no clear concept of CSR. About 20% of school principals answered that any work done by

companies or institutions is within the CSR, while some companies that have entered schools made it clear that CSR is totally different from community participation and philanthropy. The concept of CSR is closely linked to profits.

Some of the Palestinian institutions support and believe in the role of CSR in strengthening civil society, such as the Palestine Institution for Development which has an integrated program of CSR.

It is evident that the Palestinian industries and companies are under successive pressure to improve business ethics and demand greater ethics in the business of these companies. Therefore, CSR has been closely linked to the market after increasing interest in social aspects. Moreover, CSR can help increase business confidence and integrate with social activities to achieve profitable results.

It is revealed that what companies do in the aspect of their social work voluntarily maximizes the value added to society and that CSR is the responsibility of all individuals who work in the company. Therefore, CSR is linked to corporate law-abiding, environmental conservation, and community development.

This study found that 50% of the school principals believed that CSR serves as a reminder to companies of their responsibility towards their community duties. Nonetheless, 10% of the school principals opined that CSR is a voluntary initiative recognized by interested companies, while 5% of them believed that CSR is a form of corporate social suitability.

CSR may be seen from multiple angles, but it is ultimately defined as “the individual’s responsibility for the group to which one belongs.”

2. How effective is the partnership between Palestinian schools and companies in the implementation of corporate social responsibility?

The schools provided projects which have been implemented. These projects have varied according to their providers as shown in Table 1.

It is clear from Table 1 that the local community ranked first in the provision of services to public schools and its services focused on various aspects, including infrastructure, educational, environmental, and social fields. In the second place, 80 projects were presented in public institutions, particularly infrastructure to support the educational environment. Besides, there are institutions working on both sides, such as Amideast and Norwegians. The Directorate of Education ranked third in terms of projects related to education. The directorate presented a number of important projects in education to support education and teachers’ training. Also, ministries came in the fourth place. They work on specific environmental awareness programs for students. These include the Ministry of Environment and the Ministry of Industry and Trade.

Moreover, the schools themselves provided 12 projects related to the educational process and development of education. These projects were at the expense of the schools. Finally, the companies submitted 7 projects only, most of which were environmental projects. The aforementioned information was not evident in the analysis of previous projects for the training of students to acquire the necessary skills for practical education. Most of the projects were related to infrastructure, and therefore the concept of CSR for companies and schools is unclear and does not archive the required results.

Table 2 contains the number of infrastructural and educational projects that have been done in schools. It is clear from the table that 120 infrastructure projects were distributed to all schools, including projects such as building and renovation of schools, or furnishing specialized rooms, gardens, or walls. The most important are educational projects, including teacher training, student recreation, training of directors, and exhibitions of student achievement. The analysis of the data related to schools and companies indicates that most of the participation models are formulated out of content, and there is no clear role for the outcomes in general. Besides, the role of CSR in its sustainable form is absent. None of the companies and institutions provided any training program to improve the skills of students. In addition, the companies participating in schools are limited, and only 7 out of 263 projects were done. Nevertheless, there is an intention to work within the schools, but there is no proper arrangement for dealing with this work. This indicates the lack of clarity of CSR concept in schools.

Some institutions showed clear cooperation with public schools in developing students' skills, teachers' training, and school administration. This has made CSR one of the leading topics in this field. Some institutions have worked on infrastructure rehabilitation, which has played a key role in the development of schools.

3. What are the obstacles facing Palestinian schools and companies in implementing their CSR activities?

The government schools, institutions, and companies operating in these areas have faced a wide range of obstacles. The main obstacle was to allow institutions and companies to work in public schools, where they could not enter without formal permission from the Ministry of Education. This needs a long time and was often rejected. The second obstacle is the financial support from the institutions to schools. This is because any financial support must go through complex banking and bureaucratic procedures. Accordingly, school principals avoid dealing with any company or institution on financial matters.

The most problematic issue facing the training programs is the attendance of students to the company during work, which needs parental and school approval and is often rejected. The laws are strict, and students are not allowed to leave the school during the course of work for any purpose. Besides, there is no insurance coverage for students during the training. The Palestinian companies should improve the new models for CSR in schools in order to achieve the long-term sustainability of improving practical education skills.

4. What are the most important suggestions for improving, developing, and implementing CSR activities in schools?

There are a number of suggestions for companies, institutions and the Ministry of Education represented by the Directorate of Education:

1. Raising the awareness about CSR for both the principals of schools and managers of companies.
2. Establishing legislations and laws for schools in order to deal with these companies and institutions and maintain the safety of students in these institutions and companies.
3. Expanding the process of participation to include training of students within these companies, in addition to providing infrastructure or material participation.
4. Forming a committee for CSR to distribute the activities to all schools.
5. Educating parents about the importance of training in companies and institutions so that their children can participate in the activities.
6. Providing incentives by schools and institutions to students participating in internships and workshops.

2.2. Tables

Table 1, Projects implemented in schools at the Directorate of Education of North Hebron according to the concerned institutions

No	The Institution	No. of Projects
1.	Public institutions	80
2.	Companies	7
3.	Local Community	112
4.	The school itself	12
5.	Ministries	23
6.	Directorate of education	29

Table 2, Project Outputs

No.	Project type	Number of projects
1.	Infrastructure projects	120
2.	Educational projects	143

3. Discussion

It was found that there was no difference between community participation and philanthropy involvements in CSR activities. This indicates a lack of understanding of CSR aspects, which was shared by institutions,

companies, and schools. However, charity and community participation differ significantly from CSR. Companies have a specific duty in their CSR. Moreover, charitable work and community participation are open, and any company can participate. This conclusion concurs with the study conducted by Al-Aamiri (2016) which revealed that social responsibility is a phenomenon that is subject to multiple points of view. Similarly, this conclusion is consistent with Helis (2016) who dealt with the concept of social responsibility of private sector institutions in Palestine.

It is clear from the entry of companies and institutions to schools that most of the projects were related to infrastructure or financing of certain educational programs. In addition, these projects did not have a clear role in training students in order to improve their skills and teach them about professional bases, such as the commercial enterprises for commercial students and the industrial companies for vocational students. This unclear role of CSR causes a shortage of CSR practices in schools. This result concurs with the study conducted by Ismail et al. (2013) on the types of CSR for some Malaysian companies in schools were infrastructures, such as computer labs and teaching materials. It is also consistent with the findings reported by Rahal (2015), which showed that CSR constitutes a contribution to charitable work and voluntary campaigns. Similarly, the study conducted by Al-Aamiri (2016) showed that CSR is a moral obligation from companies towards the society in which they work.

It was found that there are some obstacles experienced by companies in implementing CSR activities, such as the complexity of administrative procedures imposed by the Ministry of Education. In addition, the obstacles faced by institutions and companies include financial and technical limitations, administrative procedures at schools, and federal government laws and regulations. The mechanism of applying CSR varied according to the objectives and potential of each institution and company and the prevailing environment. These obstacles must be overcome within specific suggestions made in relation to reforms within schools and in the laws of companies and their trade unions. However, the challenge remains on how to understand the social responsibility of the institutions and to what extent it should be reached, as well as the horizon from which this responsibility emanates.

4. Materials and Methods

Descriptive approach is used to determine the extent of the implementation of CSR in schools. A qualitative approach is used to describe the weaknesses and strengths of institutions and companies participating in CSR projects in government schools. Data are sourced from school reports on projects undertaken by participating institutions and companies. Other sources of data include Arabic and foreign articles and periodicals. The study highlights various perspectives of CSR in schools.

Research limitations and future research avenues

It should be noted that there are various influences of stakeholders, which can possibly determine the company's level of CSR directed toward education. This study considered only the representatives of a few companies that participate in North Hebron schools and the annual reports of these schools during the year 2017. Yet, there could be different CSR practices across several contexts. Future research could consider a different methodology, different sampling setting, and a wide area for the sample and analysis which may yield different outcomes.

Recommendations

1. There is a need to work on developing the concept of CSR by engaging in philanthropy for actual contribution to development.
2. The governmental bodies should develop a CSR index similar to that of developed countries and reward the companies that are most innovative and tender to promote competition among them in the area of social responsibility.
3. There is a need to provide the necessary material for the institutions to perform their responsibility for CSR in relation to the systems, studies, and information in light of the actual needs of society.
4. It is necessary to establish and disseminate the culture of CSR through the media, conferences, workshops, seminars and training courses to enhance expertise and share information.

5. There is a need for program planning, implementation, and coordination with relevant entities to carry out CSR and encourage the commitment of transparency.
6. It is necessary to remove restrictions that hinder the intervention of companies in schools, especially routine procedures, and shorten them in terms of time and effort as well as adopt a democratic philosophy that provides members of the community the right to participate and decide on education.
7. There is a need for shifting from centralized management to decentralization and giving the schools some powers, which could help them to open up to the society and take some decisions to open training programs for teachers and students.
8. There is a need for the development of CSR culture towards the community through the consolidation of this culture in the curricula of education and practice at the level of students.
9. There is a need to raise awareness among members of the society and parents on the importance of CSR and its role in achieving development.
10. The government should launch a program aimed at activating participation in the private sector in real partnership with the pillars of the educational process in the field of CSR.

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